

Interactive Expert Agent to Collaborate with Humans in Real-Time

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Abstract. Since infancy, humans have been acquiring motor skills and integrating tools into their bodily control, treating them as extensions of their own bodies. This learning process, known as motor learning, results in enduring enhancements in the proficiency of new motor skills, sports, music, dance, etc. The study involved both humans and agents and aimed to explore motor learning processes within a cooperative task. It also aimed to investigate the effect of agents on motor learning in which the agents are controlled by mixing the contribution of two human participants. The results show that human participants tended to view themselves as essential components of a collective entity that involves agents. Moreover, participants experience a lower Sense of Agency while collaborating with agents on tasks, indicating confirmation of emergence of we-mode.

Keywords: Motor Learning, We-mode, Sense of Agency.

1 Introduction

As social beings, humans naturally acquire new skills daily, including motor learning, which involves brain changes through physical practice, enhancing skills [1]. Ganesh et al. found that motor learning improved when participants collaborated, stressing the significance of haptic interaction [2].

Firstly, increasing the number of group members fosters collective intelligence, leading to enhanced overall performance in collaborative tasks. Collective intelligence refers to the ability of a group to achieve superior results compared to individual members working alone [3]. Secondly, diversity in control percentages over agents allows for varied levels of influence from different human participants who may experience a Sense of Agency (SoA), which denotes the perception of controlling one's actions and external events [4]. Thirdly, participation in shared tasks among humans gives rise to the phenomenon of 'we-mode' where individuals perceive themselves as integral parts of a collective entity. This collective identity can lead to faster reaction times compared to situations where individuals identify solely with themselves [5]. However, what happens when human participant interacts with agent? Under this condition, can motor learning still occur?

The study divided participants into three groups: Group 1, controlling agents statically; Group 2, with diversified control; and Group 3, with fluctuating control. They performed a basic reaching task, moving a virtual mass to a moving target using haptic arms. In the pilot study, agents controlled by fluctuated mode led to better motor learning performance than those controlled statically. The data suggests an interesting phenomenon, corroborated by questionnaire responses, where human participants perceive themselves as part of a collective that encompasses agents.

2 Method

The study, aimed at delving into motor learning processes within a cooperative task, incorporated both human participants and agents where agents are controlled by Equation 1. The agents are controlled based on three factors from the human participants: position, force, and velocity values. *Agent* represents the agent, while *Human_A* and *Human_B* denote the first and second human participants, respectively. Also, *r* expresses the contribution of human participants on controlling of the agent.

$$Agent = r * Human_A + (1 - r) * Human_B \quad (1)$$

To examine the impact of agent's control method on motor learning performance, an experimental protocol was devised following the guidelines outlined in Table 1.

Table 1. The Experiment Paradigm

		Baseline		Without Unknown Environmental Force Field Learning	BREAK	With Unknown Environmental Force Field Learning	Evaluation	
Group 1	Human (self)	Human & Human	Human & Human & Agent (Static Mode)	30 Trials		Human & Human & Agent (Static Mode)	Human & Human	Human (self)
	3 Trials	3 Trials	30 Trials		30 Trials	3 Trials	3 Trials	
Group 2	Human (self)	Human & Human	Human & Human & Agent (Diversified Mode)	30 Trials	Human & Human & Agent (Diversified Mode)	Human & Human	Human (self)	
	3 Trials	3 Trials	30 Trials		30 Trials	3 Trials	3 Trials	
Group 3	Human (self)	Human & Human	Human & Human & Agent (Fluctuated Mode)	30 Trials	Human & Human & Agent (Fluctuated Mode)	Human & Human	Human (self)	
	3 Trials	3 Trials	30 Trials		30 Trials	3 Trials	3 Trials	

All sessions are completed within a single day. At the onset of the experiment, four participants were newcomers and randomly assigned to one of three experimental groups, labelled as Group 1, Group 2, and Group 3, as detailed in Table 1. The key divergence between these groups, as indicated in Table 1, is the control algorithm utilized by the agent during the Learning Session. Subsequently, to examine adaptation to environmental dynamics, participants underwent training with and without the external force field.

In static mode, the agent mirrors the actions of human participants. Here, 'mirror' refers to the agent, akin to a child of the human participant, mimicking the action of its parent. In diversified mode, the *r* value is specified at the beginning of the experiment. These values remain the same until the end of the experiment. Additionally, in fluctuating

mode, the r value is determined by a sine wave, with each wave having unique parameters to prevent uniformity in their values.

3 Result

The pilot study results indicate higher motor learning performance with agents controlled by fluctuated mode compared to static mode (see Figure 1). Reviewing post-experiment questionnaires revealed Group 3 participants, with agents under fluctuating control, reported reduced control versus Group 1 and Group 2. This underscores the study's novelty in exploring participant perception within a group including agents. Findings support the "we-mode," indicating group integration, with lower Sense of Agency (SoA) prevailing. Consistency between findings and feedback strengthens the study's credibility regarding the we-mode's emergence. Future endeavors will involve investigating agent control based on force and velocity parameters.

Fig. 1. The graph illustrates the mean time taken for the virtual mass to reach the target in the learning session for both Group 1, Group 2 and Group 3.

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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